

UNDERSTANDING THE IMPACT OF MEME MARKETING ON CONSUMER PURCHASE INTENTION: A MODERATED-MEDIATION MODEL

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Abstract

This paper analyzes a modern form of social media marketing i.e., meme marketing, which has gained attention for its ability to entertain and engage users by integrating humor. Marketers and brands are recognizing the value of using memes as a tool to connect with its consumers. To understand the effects of meme marketing activities, this paper aims to examine the impact of meme marketing on consumer purchase intentions and subsequently assess the mediating role of consumer engagement and narrative transportation and moderating effect of brand image and meme literacy. The study encompassed 200 young Pakistani social media users with active social media accounts and familiarity with the concepts of memes and meme marketing. The study employed a quantitative methodology backed by strong statistical techniques. The method used for the analysis was structural equation modeling through SmartPLS software. The results show that consumer engagement and narrative transportation have a positive effect on purchase intention, underscoring the value of captivating and immersive content. Apart from that both moderators brand image and meme literacy, positively play a role in enhancing the engagement and narrative on consumers. Thus, the research findings hold value for companies, marketing managers and agencies that interact and engage consumers with memes and undertake meme marketing activities.

INTRODUCTION

Meme marketing, a modern concept, has emerged as a result of brands beginning to use memes in their advertising due to its increasing popularity (Ali Razaq, 2023). Social advertising or digital marketing utilizes social media platforms to promote products or services, aiming to develop engagement and build strong, personal relationships with target audiences. Unlike traditional advertising, it benefits from its interactive content, user-generated contributions, and community-driven campaigns. Memes are becoming a popular tool for social media marketing

for businesses (Kamath Charunayan, 2024). By integrating memes into the marketing strategies, businesses create a more casual, laidback, fun and relatable brand image. When used effectively, memes can boost consumer trust by aligning with cultural language, making the brand seem more authentic (mateusz kiljanczyk, 2023). Memes' shareable nature fosters higher engagement, increasing brand visibility and positive associations. Through shared humor and experiences, memes create that sense of community, enhancing consumer trust and

satisfaction. Meme marketing, involving humorous pictures, texts or videos that go viral, is increasingly crucial in connecting with younger demographics (Fernandez, 2024).

The utilization of memes by companies on social media platforms has gathered increasing attention from their intended audience. According to (Paquette, 2019), the utilization of memes in marketing results in a 30% engagement rate on social media, a significant contrast to the 1% click-through rate (CTR) observed with Google AdWords which has been the go to approach of brands for some time now. Social media channels offer an ideal environment for disseminating memes as a marketing tool. These platforms enable rapid and efficient cross-border communication, effectively delimiting the geographical boundaries. This inherent characteristic makes them a promising arena for practicing meme-based marketing (Dang, Lanxue, Chen, & Tsou, 2019). Even for a business-to-business (B2B) firm, such as Joseph Cyril Bamford (JCB) Excavators Ltd., a meme with the #JCBKiKhudai ,generated publicity worth one million dollars. Luxury brands, such as Gucci, have likewise embraced meme marketing, with the #TFWGucci (That feel when Gucci) hashtag becoming Gucci's highest engaging campaign and generating around 21,000 comments and 2 million likes across their socials. A more magnified examination of the market suggests that a diverse list of brands are now utilizing memes as a tool for engaging with their consumers and it includes luxury brands e.g., Gucci and Prada, food delivery apps e.g., Swiggy and Zomato, over-the-top (OTT) platforms such as Netflix and Amazon Prime, and dating apps like Tinder and others. Meme marketing is still a little-used and misunderstood weapon in the marketing toolbox, despite its potential to go viral

and its capacity to engage consumers more authentically. Many brands are reluctant to completely adopt meme marketing because of the strategy's inherent risk and unpredictability (Rapezzi & Matilde, 2024). Memes are fundamentally embedded in a dynamic and constantly changing online cultural landscape, where context and interpretation are susceptible to abrupt and unforeseen shifts. This raises the possibility that Internet users will misunderstand, appropriate, or even employ memes as weapons, which could lead to backlash or harm firms' reputations (Ling & Chen., 2024). In addition, it is difficult to evaluate their long-term effects on important marketing objectives like brand awareness, loyalty, and purchase intent, because memes are temporary, marketers struggle with uncertainty because they have no insight into how memes impact consumer behavior, which result in missed opportunities or failed campaigns.

Based on this the aim of the study is to understand, in the context of meme marketing, how does brand image, consumer engagement, narrative transportation and meme literacy all influence consumers' intentions to buy. More significantly the study objectives are ; (1) To investigate the relationship between narrative transportation and meme marketing. (2) To investigate the relationship between consumer engagement and meme marketing. (3) To evaluate how narrative transportation mediates the relationship between consumer purchase intention and meme marketing. (4) To evaluate how customer engagement mediates the relationship between meme marketing and consumer purchase intention. (5) To investigate how brand image moderates the link between consumer engagement and meme marketing.(6) To investigate how narrative transportation and meme marketing are influenced by meme literacy.

Figure 1: Theoretical Framework

LITERATURE REVIEW

Meme marketing has become a powerful instrument for various brands to capture their consumers’ attention in today’s digital world. Memes are gradually gaining more and more importance as an integral building block of contemporary marketing efforts that leverages humor, cultural relatability and viral content. This literature review explores the sophisticated relationship between meme marketing and consumer purchase intention, while taking into consideration the key moderators (meme literacy and brand image) and mediators (narrative transportation and consumer engagement) that affect this relationship.

Meme Marketing and Narrative Transportation:

Visual storytelling is one of the most powerful elements conveyed through Memes. Complex ideas can be conveyed quickly and effectively through a combination of images, videos and short text. The visual elements of a meme often serve as a key driver for captivating a consumer. According to study memes with thematic and symbolic elements work particularly well because they clearly convey culturally and individually relevant messages (Grigsby et al., 2023).

According to relevance theory, contextual communication is another important tool. Meme marketing that integrate well timed, context-specific associations create an emotional response in the audience immediately (Scott & Kate, 2022). For instance, brands that put forth meme marketing content that reflect the opinions of their audience

when various major local and global events are taking place may be able to achieve higher impact of narrative transportation.

Humor is one of the key factors that enhances the audience’s engagement with a story and makes the content memorable by creating a sense of fun (Malodia et al., 2022). According to study, memes that highlights a narrative that portrays shared culture can strengthen a brand’s message and make it more authentic, resulting in higher consumer engagement (Shen et al., 2024). To foster a positive consumer-brand relationship, factors like relevance, novelty, and consistency of the narrative are key to determine how consumers interact with memes (Houghton et al., 2023). Marketers can create a deeper relationship by focusing on these informational cues, however an overly sarcastic content can weaken the brand’s relationship with their consumers.

Meme Marketing and Consumer Engagement:

According to resonance theory, cognitive resonance have great importance in enhancing consumer response. Memes bring to mind positive emotions, by combining the aspect of amusement and relatability in both cultural and personal context. These experiences promote consumers to actively engage with the memes, evoking positive emotions which motivates them to comment, share, or even get inspired by the original meme and create similar content meme (Kitajima et al., 2021). These positive emotions strengthen the relationship with the consumers leading to greater engagement over time.

For instance, well known brands like Wendy's and Coca Cola also opt for similar marketing efforts. Such as Wendy's using memes to interact with its customers and Coca Cola's campaign called "share a coke" that encourages customer initiative names (Bowo et al., 2024).

Uses and gratifications theory provides an insight into how meme marketing is successful at engaging consumers from a theoretical perspective (Mohammed & Ali, 2023). Memes can easily satisfy a consumer's need for amusement, escapism and social connection when using social media which further draws them to meme marketing. Humorous aspect of meme marketing acts as a gratification mechanism, which makes sure that it not only increases engagement but also encourages consumers to positively associate with the brand.

The gradual but notable increase in the number of companies using meme-driven platforms to promote their businesses shows how valuable meme marketing is in the present business environment. Due to their innate quality to go viral, marketers see the potential to spread awareness about their organization on social media comparatively quickly to other marketing tools. This ability to spread quickly due to its novel and unique nature, brands are able to not only increase engagement but also strengthen brand recall (Rathi & Jain, 2023). Memes that tend to strike a deep chord within a customer's mind have the ability to stay with them for a longer time. Memes can gradually sustain engagement by capturing a consumer's attention and increasing loyalty to the brand which results in repeat business.

Meme Literacy Moderates the significant Relationship Between Meme Marketing and Narrative Transportation:

Meme literacy is the ability to easily understand, analyze, and interact with memes in a digital culture. There are some important elements of meme literacy, among those one is cultural knowledge, which enables people to identify the allusions, the contexts and the patterns found in memes. Another important element is humor decoding, since memes frequently use sarcasm, irony and comedy to get their points across. Moreover, understanding how memes change with time, including how to differentiate

between various meme generations like those that are character-based, emoji-based or narrative-driven is another essential aspect of meme literacy (Lestari, et al., 2024).

The capability to understand the cultural, social, and political consequences ingrained in these digital artifacts is what makes literacy so important when analyzing meme narratives. Memes frequently convey nuanced meanings that are influenced by satire also known as dark comedy and relatable humor. This calls for a sophisticated understanding of the content as well as the environment in which it is being shared. By understanding how memes impact the opinion of the public and reflect cultural values, those people with meme literacy, are able to decipher or decode these multi-layered meanings (leiser, 2022). While some people might find it more difficult to relate, which could lessen the meme's ability to effectively communicate its intended message, other people, who are more familiar with meme culture and have more digital exposure are more likely to interact with that same narrative on a deeper level (Tidy et al., 2024). Designing inclusive and effective meme-based communication tactics requires an understanding of these differences in meme literacy. The study shows that those who are more meme literate are better able to participate in and contribute to these co-created narratives, which results in more effective communication and deeper narrative transportation (Copland, 2024).

Brand image moderates the significant relationship between meme marketing and Consumer Engagement.

The way that brand image mitigates the beneficial correlation between meme marketing and customer engagement is a crucial factor to take into account. Through humor, relatability and relevance, memes i.e., amusing digital content which possess viral qualities, influence consumer attitudes and actions. The effectiveness of meme marketing is strongly determined by how well the meme corresponds with or is in line with a company's established image, since consumers may respond differently based on their opinion of brand legitimacy and brand consistency. The firm must also make sure that the underlying tone and humor of memes are consistent

with the company's identity (Alanood Almaghlouth, 2024).

A strong brand image can boost customer trust and engagement with memes, but a misaligned, inconsistent or weak brand image may limit the effectiveness of such methods. Some studies show that internal behavioral motives triggered by memes, such as escapism, self-concept, perceived pleasure and social fulfillment, are very important for consumer brand engagement. However, depending on the brand image, these effects may be either increased or lessened.

The impact of meme-driven content is strengthened by a solid brand image, which guarantees and ensures consistency and legitimacy in customer perceptions of brand. On the other hand, a mismatch between brand image and meme-based content could make engagement less successful. As a result, even if meme marketing is an effective technique for engaging consumers, its effectiveness depends on how well it complements and upholds the brand's image (Pandey, 2024).

Mediating Role of Narrative Transportation in Relation between Meme Marketing and Consumer Purchase Intention:

The story telling aspect of a meme plays a mediating role in the relationship between meme marketing and consumer purchase intentions by encouraging consumer involvement with branded content. Narrative transportation refers to the emotional and cognitive process in which consumers immerse themselves in a story, leading them to have an experience that they remember more vividly and with an amplified impact. With respect to meme marketing, narrative transportation occurs when a meme successfully conveys a story or plot that identifies profoundly with what consumer's experience in their personal lives (Houghton et al., 2023).

With reference to (Yang & Kang, 2021), marketing through the means of storytelling has become an increasingly widespread tool and a creative yet affordable way to get people engaged with a brand. The phenomenon of narrative transportation successfully acts as a mediator between meme marketing and consumer purchase intent. Employing humorous and creative content that is also culturally

relatable in meme marketing results in a higher likelihood for consumers to be emotionally immersed and form a stronger relationship the firm in question.

Meme marketing strengthens the campaign's impact by making it unforgettable and compelling, this form of engagement mediated by story transmission or narrative transportation increases the probability that people will make a purchase.

Mediating Role of Consumer Engagement in Relation between Meme Marketing and Consumer Purchase Intention:

The mediating role of consumer engagement in relation between meme marketing and consumer purchase intention is valuable, according to research on marketing and consumer purchase intention. An advanced and interactive social space is gradually replacing traditional physical and online stores, where people are willing to learn about the brand from one another (Fang et al., 2021). Social media is now the primary computer-assisted communication platform and plays a big part in people's daily lives. Given that social media benefits all parties including businesses, brands, consumers, and advertisers, it presents a lot of opportunities (Abbasi et al., 2023).

Furthermore, active users are more likely to engage with the content which increases the content's reach and brand's word of mouth, which in turn positively influences the consumer's purchase intention. Research indicates that E-WOM has significant impact on consumer purchase intention, highlighting the importance of consumer product knowledge (Shafa et al., 2023).

According to (Onofrei et al., 2022), C2C or consumer to consumer interactions have an impact on consumers' digital engagement and goods or service purchase intentions, particularly when they involve other like-minded customers who are regarded as knowledgeable and trustworthy. . Impact of consumer-to-consumer (C2C) interactions on behavioral engagement combined with content quality and source credibility serving as mediators is significant.

The primary focus of this research is to explore the impact of meme marketing on consumer purchase intention, while being mediated by consumer engagement and narrative transportation; further moderated by brand image and meme literacy respectively. Therefore, the study examines the hypotheses that were formulated following a detailed literature review (see figure 1 for a visual representation of these hypotheses).

H1: Meme marketing has a direct significant impact on narrative transportation.

H2: Meme marketing has a direct significant impact on consumer engagement.

H3: Meme literacy moderates the positive relationship between meme marketing and narrative transportation.

H4: Brand image moderates the positive relationship between meme marketing and consumer engagement.

H5: Narrative transportation mediates the significant relationship between meme marketing and consumer purchase intention.

H6: Consumer engagement mediates the significant relationship between meme marketing and consumer purchase intention.

METHODOLOGY

With an emphasis on how self-related aspects impact consumer behavior and perceptions in the digital sphere, this study attempts to examine the effects of meme marketing on the purchase intentions of graduate students in Lahore, Pakistan. It utilizes a cross-sectional research design, gathering data at one point in time. The target group of this study is business and media undergraduate students in three

institutes of Lahore namely Kinnaird College for Women, Lahore School of Economics and Lahore University of Management Sciences, who are actively engaged in online activities, especially those related to consumption and sharing of memes. The majority of participants are between the ages of teenage and young adulthood. 200 participants were judged to be a sufficient enough sample size based on the 20 items in the survey, in accordance with item-response theory, for ensuring reliability and generalizability of results. Purposive and convenience sampling approaches are used in data collecting; the former makes it easier to locate people who interact with memes, while the latter guarantees that respondents have a specific interest in meme culture, increasing the findings' applicability. The study aims to provide a thorough grasp of the effects of meme marketing on this particular audience by integrating various approaches. Data collection will be through self-administered electronic surveys ensuring ethical standards and confidentiality of participants. Main constructs of study include meme marketing, consumer engagement, narrative transportation, meme literacy, brand image, consumer purchase intention and will be used with the same standardized scales, where available. Because of its ease of use and strong ability to manage intricate statistical processes in primary research, Smart PLS is chosen as the main statistical tool for the analysis. Overall, the data will provide insights to marketers as to how the usage of meme marketing—a contemporary marketing tool—coupled with engagement and narrative transportation influences purchase decisions of consumers.

Table 1 -Scale and Measurement

	Variables	No. of items	Author
1.	Meme Marketing	3	(Rathi & Jain, 2024)
2.	Meme literacy	3	(Latif & Suryani, 2024)
3.	Brand image	4	(Latif & Suryani, 2024)
4.	Narrative transportation	3	(Razzaq et al., 2024)
5.	Consumer engagement	4	(Rathi & Jain, 2024)
6.	Consumer purchase intention	3	(Rathi & Jain, 2024)

DATA ANALYSIS RESULTS

When analyzing the reliability of various s factors in meme marketing, Table 2 shows that brand image has a composite reliability value of 0.894 and a Cronbach’s alpha of 0.842. Similarly, consumer engagement has a composite reliability, also known as construct reliability, of 0.825 and a Cronbach’s alpha of 0.721. Consumer purchase intention has a construct reliability of 0.888 and a Cronbach’s alpha of 0.811. Meme literacy has a construct reliability of 0.837 and a Cronbach’s alpha of 0.709. Meme Marketing has a construct reliability of 0.881 and a Cronbach’s alpha of 0.796. Narrative Transportation has a construct reliability of 0.896 and a Cronbach’s alpha of 0.826. Overall, most of the variables have a higher reliability value than required. A widely agreed-upon guideline or threshold is that a reliability coefficient

ranging from 0.6-0.7 is considered acceptable, while a coefficient of 0.8 or higher is considered optimal (Ursachi, George, Horodnic, & Zait, 2015). Also, according to (Nguyen, Thinh, Nguyen, & Pervan, 2020), the average variance extracted (AVE) in an analysis should be greater than 0.5 to meet the minimum threshold. On the other hand, they also suggest that if the AVE in the analysis is less than 0.5, but the composite reliability is more than 0.6, the construct still has enough convergent validity. The average variance for brand image is 0.679, consumer engagement has average variance of 0.542, consumer purchase intention has average variance of 0.725, meme literacy has average variance of 0.632, meme marketing has average variance of 0.712 and lastly narrative transportation has average variance of 0.742.

Table 2: Reliability Analysis

	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
Brand Image	0.842	0.894	0.679
Consumer Engagement	0.721	0.825	0.542
Consumer Purchase Intention	0.811	0.888	0.725
Meme Literacy	0.709	0.837	0.632
Meme Marketing	0.796	0.881	0.712
Narrative Transportation	0.826	0.896	0.742

The study determined that the correlation analysis is strong for all variables as the Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) ratio serves as an indicator for evaluating discriminant validity in structural equation modelling (Voorhees et al., 2016). HTMT levels must fall below a certain threshold, which is 0.90. The findings demonstrate that every value is below 0.90 that is good. Consequently, discriminant validity can be established under HTMT as shown in

table 3. The correlation matrix sheds light on how important structural equation model constructs relate to one another. Overall, the results demonstrate the powerful independent benefits of meme marketing on brand image, and they imply that narrative transportation and meme literacy are critical for increasing customer engagement and buy intention.

Table 3: Correlation Analysis- Discriminant Validity

	Brand Image	Consumer Engagement	Consumer Purchase Intention	Meme Literacy	Meme Marketing	Narrative Transportation
Brand Image	-					
Consumer Engagement	0.690	-				
Consumer Purchase Intention	0.703	0.565	-			
Meme Literacy	0.766	0.575	0.589	-		
Meme Marketing	0.586	0.638	0.468	0.491	-	
Narrative Transportation	0.598	0.600	0.598	0.538	0.740	-

The path analysis indicates some important connections between consumer engagement, narrative transportation, brand image, meme marketing and consumer purchase intention (see table 4) . Both brand image [$\beta = 0.409, p = 0.000$] and meme marketing [$\beta = 0.295, p = 0.000$] significantly boost consumer engagement. Their combined effect is also very considerable [$\beta = 0.168, p = 0.000$], indicating that the effectiveness of meme marketing increases in the presence of a strong brand image. Consumer engagement [$\beta = 0.280, p = 0.000$]

and narrative transportation [$\beta = 0.360, p = 0.000$] have a positive effect on purchase intention, underscoring the value of captivating and immersive content. Meme literacy [$\beta = 0.215, p = 0.000$] enhances narrative transportation, and its interaction with meme marketing [$\beta = 0.155, p = 0.000$] further promotes immersion. Meme marketing has a strong influence on narrative transportation [$\beta = 0.524, p = 0.000$], emphasizing its significance in brand storytelling.

Table 4 Complete Path Analysis

	Path coefficients	P value
Brand Image -> Consumer Engagement	0.409	0.000
Brand Image x Meme Marketing -> Consumer Engagement	0.168	0.000
Consumer Engagement -> Consumer Purchase Intention	0.280	0.000
Meme Literacy -> Narrative Transportation	0.215	0.000
Meme Literacy x Meme Marketing -> Narrative Transportation	0.155	0.000
Meme Marketing -> Consumer Engagement	0.295	0.000
Meme Marketing -> Narrative Transportation	0.524	0.000
Narrative Transportation -> Consumer Purchase Intention	0.360	0.000

Summary of results

No.	Hypothesis Statements	Results
01	H1: Meme marketing has a direct positive impact on narrative transportation.	Supported
02	H2: Meme marketing has a direct positive impact on consumer engagement.	Supported
03	H3: Narrative transportation mediates the positive relationship between meme marketing and consumer purchase intention.	Supported
04	H4: Consumer engagement mediates the positive relationship between meme marketing and consumer purchase intention.	Supported
05	H5: Brand image moderates the positive relationship between meme marketing and consumer purchase intention.	Supported
06	H6: Brand image moderates the positive relationship between meme marketing and consumer purchase intention.	Supported

DISCUSSIONS

This study’s main goal was to investigate the connections among consumer purchase intention and meme literacy, and how narrative transportation, brand image, consumer engagement, meme marketing impacts their relationships. The results pertaining to consumer engagement, brand image, narrative transportation, meme literacy and meme marketing will be discussed in the sections that follow, along with how these elements affect consumers' intentions to make purchases. The results of the data analysis will be used to explore each hypothesis, emphasizing its theoretical and practical ramifications.

The first hypothesis, stating that meme marketing directly influences storytelling, was strongly sustained ($\beta = 0.525, p = 0.000$). This support with prior findings that memes sarcastic or entertaining content draws consumers into brand narratives. Memes act as an individual storytelling tools, increasing message

recall and engagement, thus proposing significant implications for marketers. The second hypothesis, that meme marketing improves consumer engagement, was authenticated ($\beta = 0.295, p = 0.000$). Related meme content motivates consumers to engage with brands. The viral nature of memes nurtures a sense of belonging and existence, supporting their part in enhancing engagement. The third hypothesis was definite, with narrative transportation meaningfully mediating the relationship between meme marketing and purchase intention ($\beta = 0.360, p = 0.000$). Being drawn into a brand’s story through memes rises the likelihood of purchase, emphasizing the double role of memes in entertainment and encouragement. The fourth hypothesis, that engagement mediates the link between meme marketing and purchase intention, was supported ($\beta = 0.280, p = 0.000$). Engaging with meme content develops belief and emotional connection, converting it to higher purchase intent.

Marketers should produce content that entertains and inspires participation. The fifth hypothesis was validated ($\beta = 0.168$, $p = 0.000$), displaying that brand image impacts how effectively meme marketing pushes purchase intention. Well-known brands have more from meme campaigns, making it dynamic to align memes with encouraging or positive brand identity. Lastly it was found that meme literacy develops the effect of meme marketing on storytelling ($\beta = 0.155$, $p = 0.000$). Consumers that are familiar with meme culture are more endorsed in narratives conveyed through memes, highlighting the need to target digitally fluent demographics.

There are a number of restrictions to take into account, even if this study offers intuitive information about the connections among consumer involvement, brand image, narrative transportation, meme marketing, and purchase intention. This study mainly focused on younger, digitally native individuals, limiting generalizability. Ethnic context may also affect meme reaction. The cross-sectional design captures only a moment in time, does not cater long term effects. Also, measuring engagement through likes, comments, and shares may not fully imitate deeper connection like emotional or cognitive engagement.

Some aspects to explore for future studies; Include wider demographics to safeguard generalizability. Conduct cross-cultural studies to comprehend meme efficiency altogether. Use longitudinal designs to measure long-term effects. Discover emotional and cognitive engagement outside surface metrics. Explore how personality behaviors (e.g., humor preference) and meme formats (image, video, and text) affect results.

Stranded in the Elaboration Likelihood Model (ELM) and Uses and Gratifications Theory (UGT), the study proposes that memes, as peripheral cues, effect attitudes via entertainment and relatability. Meme marketing impacts consumer behavior through narrative transportation and engagement, moderated by brand image and meme literacy. This study delivers actionable insights for digital marketers, mainly in Pakistan. Memes, when aligned with brand identity and cultural significance, can lift engagement and purchase intention. Brands should reflect meme literacy and narrative strength when making campaigns.

CONCLUSION

This study observed how meme marketing affects purchase intention, concentrating on narrative transportation, engagement, brand image, and meme literacy. Using data from 200 respondents, all six hypotheses were definite. While memes can drive deeper engagement and purchase intent, limitations such as sample bias and ethnic specificity exist. Future studies should broaden scope and depth. Generally, memes, when considerately crafted, serve as operative tools for digital storytelling and persuasion

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